

MOBIDATALAB

Labs for prototyping future mobility data sharing solutions in the cloud

D6.6 Project Cooperation Activities Report #1

**Document of all interactions with other EU/International projects,
initiatives and networks.**

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Summary sheet

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I Project Partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
AKKA I&S	France	AKKA
POLIS - PROMOTION OF OPERATIONAL LINKS WITH INTEGRATED SERVICES	Belgium	POLIS
F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	Ireland	F6S

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Executive Summary

This report documents all interactions with other EU/International projects, initiatives and networks, carried out within the related task T6.5.

MobiDataLab seeks to liaise thematically with other projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond, at national, European and international levels. The identification of other interesting and relevant initiatives is enabled through the project's knowledge-building activities and from the recruited stakeholders. The format and outcome of this cooperation effort can take several forms (sharing of methodology, research findings, joint presentations or even joint events). The project is expected to cooperate with, **at least, 3 projects and initiatives per year** (a total of 9), and all activities will be summarised in the report (D6.7) at the end of the project.

- With the submission of this deliverable, the **MobiDataLab partners collaborated with 6 projects or initiatives** for i) the organisation of online events (co-organisation of online events or mutual participation in each-other events), ii) sharing dissemination channels to reach the target audiences and promote projects results (i.e., mutual support in dissemination, website, social networks, etc), and iii) knowledge transfer, such as tips on how to maximise the impact of project activities.
- These collaborations have contributed to the success of MobiDataLab's activities by gathering relevant insights, increasing the visibility of the communication campaigns, and enhancing the impact of project events.
- The present document highlights the projects and initiatives that have actively collaborated with MobiDataLab and outlines the scope of these collaborations and their impact.
- The content is organised in two main sections, one presenting the methodology and plan, while the other one covers synergies established, future perspectives and lessons learned in terms of how to identify synergies and create collaborations, and how to get maximum outcome from the collaborations.

Related milestone has been achieved in the process, described as follows:

- **Milestone 16 (MS16):** Cooperation with other projects. Mean of verification: cooperation is established by tangible actions such as the exchange of data or joint workshops to share practices around transport data

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I Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab

Introduction

1.1. Project Overview

1.

There has been an explosion of mobility services and data sharing in recent years. Building on this, the EU-funded MobiDataLab project works to foster the sharing of data amongst transport authorities, operators and other mobility stakeholders in Europe. MobiDataLab develops knowledge as well as a cloud solution aimed at easing the sharing of data. Specifically, the project is based on a continuous co-development of knowledge and technical solutions. It collects and analyses the advice and recommendations of experts and supporting cities, regions, clusters and associations. These actions are assisted by the incremental construction of a cross-thematic knowledge base and a cloud-based service platform, which will improve access and usage of data-sharing resources.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

The goal of this deliverable is to report on the synergies and exchange of experiences established with other initiatives during the first 18 months of the MobiDataLab project implementation. It is important to note that this is the first of two Deliverables that will be submitted with the same purpose, to report on MobiDataLab cooperation activities, being the second one delivered by the end of the project (month 36).

1.3. Intended Audience

D6.6 'Project cooperation activities report #1' is a public deliverable addressed to the MobiDataLab project partners and to the several actors of the mobility sectors that aim to contribute to an improved data sharing culture and to the digitalization of the transport sector.

1.4. Structure of the deliverable and Relation with other Work Packages/Deliverable

This document first presents the rationale behind MobiDataLab's cooperation strategy, as included in the Deliverable 6.1 Dissemination Plan (May 2021, M4). It then describes in detail each collaboration activity by MobiDataLab and other European initiatives, between February 2021 (M1) and July 2022 (M18). Finally, it exposes the lessons learned from such collaborations for the project so far and showcases the planned collaborations for 2022 and 2023.

The deliverable takes input from: D6.1 Dissemination plan and D6.2 'Reporting on MobiDataLab events #1', and the deliverable provides output to: D6.3 'Reporting on MobiDataLab events #2', D6.4 'Reporting on MobiDataLab events #3', and D6.7 'Project cooperation activities report #2'.

Cooperation Methodology

2.1. Rationale as included in the Dissemination Plan

MobiDataLab seeks to liaise thematically and establish synergies with other EU projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond. This may result in collaborations such as the co-organisation of events, the involvement of representatives of such initiatives in the MobiDataLab project (and vice versa), sharing of knowledge and best practices, and the cross-promotion of activities and results, in an increased outreach of the project outcomes. The project is expected to cooperate with, at least, 3 projects and initiatives per year (a total of 9).

The monitoring of this activity is done by F6S, with the support of all project partners, and the involvement of further project partners in the cooperation process is done on a case-by-case need, after the joint identification of the collaboration pathways between both parties.

Project partners are thus asked to inform F6S, as task leader, and POLIS, as WP leader, of any potential collaboration, and provide the necessary content for scheduling an initial meeting and further developing the collaboration.

A Collaboration Log has been created, for regular monitoring and reporting on the progress of cooperation initiatives. Also, a partnership page on the project's website is made (see Figure 1), to showcase the collaborations established and the work jointly developed.

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MobiDataLab is seeking to liaise thematically with other projects and initiatives from Horizon 2020 and beyond, at national, European and international level. The identification of other interesting and relevant initiatives is enabled through the project's knowledge building activities, and from the recruited stakeholders. The format and outcome of this cooperation effort takes several forms (common promotion support, sharing of methodology, research findings, joint presentations or even joint events).

All cooperation activities will be summarised in report at the end of the project.

MobiDataLab has currently launched cooperation with the following projects and initiatives:

REACH
NEXT GENERATION DATA INCUBATOR

Figure 1. MobiDataLab Website Partnership Page

Cooperation Activities Plan

3.1. Establishing Contact with Related Projects

3.

As the overall objective of MobiDataLab is “to propose to the **mobility stakeholders** a methodology and tools that foster the development of a data sharing culture in Europe and beyond,” it is also important to acknowledge **ongoing related projects** and the need to coordinate and collaborate with these to avoid potential duplication and to maximise impact. In line with Task 6.5 “Cooperation with other projects and initiatives”, MobiDataLab will:

- Establish contact and cooperation with further projects, and programmes, relevant to this project and particularly related initiatives within, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe, and other EC-funded programmes and intra-organisation initiatives.
- Coordinate with other related projects as facilitated by the partners and their wider networks to access members of different organisations with different interests and focus points.
- Track the results of cooperation with other projects as an item for discussion on the agenda at each Work Package 6 meeting. F6S will maintain oversight of progress on liaising with other projects and will seek to ensure that all opportunities for collaboration are harnessed.

F6S, as leader of Task 6.5 “Cooperation with other projects and initiatives” will be required to organise, manage and delegate responsibility for consortium members to make contact with related projects. Initially, contact can be made by email with formal correspondence by way of an invitation to cooperate and collaborate.

3.2. Possible Collaboration Approaches

Collaboration within research-related projects has far-reaching benefits. Collaboration provides a seamless link between universities and research institutions, industry, commerce, government and public services. Collaboration occurs at various levels including individuals, groups, departments, institutions, sectors and countries. Some collaboration is formal, and much more is informal. There are **three possible approaches** to cooperation to be adopted in the MobiDataLab project:

- **Corporate Partnership:** meaning, wide access to external resources and influencers. This will deal with the relevant project on an entire project basis, i.e., management of the MobiDataLab project collaborating with the management of a selected project.
- **Team Collaboration:** meaning, research problem and people focused). This will involve a specific WP or Task team collaborating with contributors to a specific WP in another project working on an identified task where overlaps with the MobiDataLab project have been identified. This collaboration may also come in the form of a MobiDataLab task team working closely with specific members of a relevant project where technical expertise on a subject or exchange of ideas may be obtained from the collaboration efforts.
- **Personal Collaboration:** meaning, research problem and people focused.

MobiDataLab will look to achieve a combination of the above approaches as it looks to engage with a range of stakeholders, projects, and organisations. The MobiDataLab consortium members are encouraged to develop collaboration approaches under any of the above-listed categories which they feel will be beneficial to achieving the project outputs.

3.3. Project Cooperation Aims and Forms

Through inter-project cooperation, the project can benefit in numerous ways. As the project will be developing a new methodology and tools, inter-project collaboration is vital for refining what the final MobiDataLab outputs as related to the development of a data-sharing culture will look like. This will help to avoid issues such as duplication or scope slippage, especially concerning the tools of other research projects in the mobility data domain.

MobiDataLab aims to engage in inter-project collaboration to achieve the following:

- A more integrated or coordinated approach to stakeholder needs, wider geographical reach and access to new stakeholder groups who would not have previously been included in the scope of the project.
- Financial savings in terms of dissemination and integration of existing knowledge and expertise.
- Knowledge, good practice and information sharing, and the capacity to replicate success more vastly and quickly.
- To build a stronger, united voice in the field of mobility data research.
- Better coordination of project activities, competitive advantage, and mutual support between organisations.

Following preparatory work, during the meetings that were held, MobiDataLab presented to the other projects the following **forms to consider regarding collaboration**:

- High-level workshops (e.g., Coordinators' Meetings, Technical Groups' Meetings);
- Joint activities (e.g., common (final) events, webinars, policy sessions, joint newsletters, online editions, publications and press releases, hosting of articles);
- Advisory Services (e.g., Formal advisors to each other);
- Exchange of information on stakeholders' mapping, and
- Projects' social media and communication efforts to be connected and mutually supported.

However, a further set of possibilities has been already processed and, in the future might be put into the discussion. Namely, the following organisational and performance management options:

- Specify, in writing, a short roadmap and particularly specific goals (“aspirations” of collaboration);
- Set smart objectives (most importantly measurable and time-specific objectives);
- Specify a wider set of joint activities, and
- Define output indicators (numerical values for the outputs of collaboration) and result indicators (tangible/measurable results).

In other words, instead of a “vague” collaboration, this may have a specific “framework” of operations and indicators of success.

3.4. Management of Collaboration Activities

The management of the MobiDataLab collaboration activities will be mainly carried out under Task 6.5 ‘Cooperation with other projects and initiatives in WP6, which covers communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the MobiDataLab project.

This WP task, and hence the coordination activity, is being led by F6S, with contributions from POLIS, and AKKA. To ensure that the MobiDataLab project maintains its strategic direction and to enhance the collaboration with other relevant projects, all partners are invited to participate.

Results and outputs produced from the collaboration between the MobiDataLab consortium and other relevant projects and initiatives on a project, team/task or personal level will be tracked and recorded via the Cooperation Log. More monitoring information can be found in Section 6.

For personal and task-level collaborative approaches between MobiDataLab consortium members and other relevant project partners, the MobiDataLab task leader (F6S) is responsible for representing the consortium at collaboration meetings (where practicable) and is tasked with arranging and managing the coordination of the specific meeting.

4. Summary of Synergies and Collaborations

This section summarises the synergies and collaborations that MobiDataLab established with other initiatives and stakeholders, during the different activities of the project. Emphasis is given to the potential interest and impact achieved.

Down the line, Table 1 represents the summary of all synergies and collaborations carried out in MobiDataLab.

Table 1. Summary of MobiDataLab Synergies and Collaborations

Initiative Name	Project/Initiative Description	Potential Interest for MobiDataLab
DataPorts	DataPorts will provide a Data Platform in which transportation and logistics companies around a seaport will be able to manage data like any other company asset, to create the basis to offer cognitive services.	Impact on the activities carried out under Task 3.4 ‘Data Sharing Business and revenue models.
Molière	Molière will build the world's best open data commons for mobility services, the “Wikipedia of public transport and new mobility data”, a Mobility Data	Exchange knowledge and best practices between both projects. Cross-dissemination activities. Complementarity in terms of the

	Marketplace (MDM) underpinned by blockchain technology.	organisation of hackathons and datathons.
SoBigData++	The project will deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data to understand the complexity of our society. SoBigData++ will produce tools and services to empower researchers and innovators through a platform of data and algorithms sharing.	Exploit the results in terms of know-how on a platform for sharing datasets and analysis methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases.
MASTER	The overarching objective of MASTER is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of organisations working on a joint research programme to define new methods to build, manage and analyse multiple aspects of semantic trajectories.	Build on the research results regarding the semantic enrichment activities. Specifically, on the new concept of multiple aspects trajectories methods, methods to manage these kinds of mobility data and analysis like for example prediction based on Machine Learning, similarity methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases.
SYN+AIR	SYN+AIR aims to develop common sets for data sharing between transport service providers (TSPs), enabling passengers to enjoy a seamless door-to-door travel experience	Work together to add data transformation endpoints to the architecture of the Smart Contracts Framework solution presented
REACH Incubator	The REACH project will launch a sustainable European second-generation incubator for data-fuelled start-ups and SMEs to develop innovative experiments within data value chains. The project expects to attract more than 500 data-driven concept applications and select 100 business ideas	Have access to a pool of data-driven start-ups and SMEs to engage within the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs

4.1. Collaboration with the DataPorts Project

Focused on European seaports, **DataPorts** (dataports-project.eu) tries to tackle specific data-related challenges of daily seaport management involving many stakeholders and operators that need to share data, such as the lack of methods for secure and trustworthy sharing of data or the reduction of administrative burdens through data sharing, among others. The project intends to tackle these challenges by building an Industrial Data Platform in which transportation and logistics companies around a seaport will be able to manage data like any other company asset, to create the basis to offer cognitive services.

There are, thus, clear complementarities between both projects, as they aim at identifying the needed platforms, tools and standards to facilitate data sharing within a specific sector in Europe. Both agreed to continue to share knowledge and best practices on relevant topics, such as new business and revenue models for data sharing, to best provide a framework to support the respective stakeholders to take advantage of the data produced from their network and improve their operations and services.

Santiago Cáceres of DataPorts joined the 1st MobiDataLab webinar (Figure 2), where he presented the Project, and joined the discussion about the challenges and opportunities of data sharing between actors in transport, mobility, and other sectors.

Figure 2. The DataPorts Project at the 1st MobiDataLab Webinar

After the exchange of best practices and knowledge regarding business and revenue models, there was a group discussion on other topics that MobiDataLab and DataPorts found interesting to keep track of and exchange knowledge and best practices. These are as follows: Transport Cloud, Data access and data processors, Interoperability framework, and IDS reference architectural model. Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

4.2. Collaboration with the Molière Project

With the ambition of promoting sustainable, affordable, equitable, and accessible mobility by making more data available, **Molière** (moliere-project.eu) wants to create a Mobility Data Marketplace (a «Wikipedia» for mobility data), with the inclusion of a blockchain layer for trust, security and safety of the data exchanged between users within the marketplace, and test its implementation in several use cases in European cities.

There are, thus, clear synergies between both projects, as they aim at a new mobility paradigm, and both agreed to continue to share knowledge and best practices on relevant topics, such as new business and revenue models for data sharing, market status – mobility data sharing companies, products and services currently operating in the EU market, regulatory and legal needs, challenges and frameworks, data needs from mobility actors and how they can cooperate, organisation of hackathons, among others.

It was the Molière project that got in touch with MobiDataLab, after also applying for the project's Reference Group. MobiDataLab reached out and a video call was scheduled for the 22nd of October 2021. After the general presentation of both projects, there was a group discussion on the possible synergies to explore between both projects in the short and long term.

In the short term, with a communication focus, Molière Project Coordinator proposed to do a joint article and social media posts on the clear synergies between both projects, that address the same hot topic of mobility data sharing. The goal was to write an article stating that both projects are addressing similar topics, and how their research is being put into practice in a similar (and sometimes very different) way.

In the long-term, Molière is interested in learning more about the research conducted by AETHON on the actors' needs, so AETHON agreed on sending the one-pager regarding this task. Due to its market orientation, HOVE also pointed out its interest in having a follow-up meeting to discuss the topic of business and revenue models (as in Task 3.4), and to exchange knowledge and best practices. This would be a 1-hour session, looking at what was already produced from Molière's side and how they have addressed some of the issues related to this topic (i.e., required levels of trust between different mobility stakeholders: why should private and public players share their data with each other? What are the incentives?).

Josep Laborda, Molière Project Coordinator, joined the 1st MobiDataLab webinar (Figure 3), where he presented the Project, and joined the discussion about the challenges and opportunities of data sharing between actors in the transport, mobility, and other sectors.

Figure 3. The Molière Project at the 1st MobiDataLab Webinar

Moreover, there is a clear complementarity in terms of the organisation of hackathons and datathons. Although Molière already organized theirs, they are interested in taking part in the concept development and organisation of those of MobiDataLab. In terms of timing, AETHON informed us that the concept and organisation plan will be done until August 2022 and then the living labs are expected to start in February 2023, with the organisation of the first hackathon event. With the possible extension of 6 more months of the Molière project, there could be a clear overlap in the activities of both projects regarding these activities, so both projects decided to keep in touch and MobiDataLab will make sure to send information to Molière regarding these events. Furthermore, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

4.3. Collaboration with the SoBigData++ Project

This project **SoBigData++** (sobigdata.eu) is the second version of the one that started in 2015 to create a research infrastructure that made it possible for researchers in the EU to access data, with both URV and CNR being consortium partners. Even though there are a lot of platforms for data, it

is difficult to join all the needed features in a common way if you are a researcher (and even harder if you are from the industry). SoBigData++, thus, tries to enlarge the services this research infrastructure provides to all of Europe, by combining data-driven and model-driven approaches when providing data to researchers. The project is trying to create a place where researchers can experiment with data provided by other researchers, based on a responsible open data science approach: the experiments done in the scope of SoBigData++ are ethical and according to EU rules, and of open access.

MobiDataLab reached out and a video call was scheduled on the 9th of November, 2021, and after the general presentation of both projects, there was a group discussion on the possible synergies to explore between both projects in the short and long term.

First, it would be relevant to investigate possible interactions “machine to machine” between both projects’ data catalogues. The projects can also collaborate in the sharing of metadata information on the catalogue, organisation of several events, participation at SoBigData++’s summer school (to have people for the hackathons), sharing of approaches and exchange of information between both projects, although SoBigData++ is more oriented towards building research infrastructure and have researchers using that infrastructure and MobiDataLab is more market-oriented.

The availability of data (accessing data, sharing data, obtaining data) is also a common point. MobiDataLab has good contacts with cities, transport operators, etc., with challenges, which could be good for SoBigData++ and the researchers they support. Also, SoBigData++ has a platform for the organisation of hackathons and the use of their data, which might be relevant for MobiDataLab, so both projects could consider the organisation of a hackathon. Moreover, MobiDataLab could also publish metadata in SoBigData’s data catalogue.

Roberto Trasarti, the SoBigData++ Project Coordinator, joined the 1st MobiDataLab webinar (Figure 4), where he presented the Project, and joined the discussion about the challenges and opportunities of data sharing between actors in the transport, mobility, and other sectors.

Figure 4. The SoBigData++ Project at the 1st MobiDataLab Webinar

In addition, on June 10th, 2021, AKKA participated in the 4th SoBigData++ Awareness Panel (Figure 5). Thierry Chevallier of AKKA discussed decentralised anonymisation of mobility data, data sovereignty in the connected vehicle, studying population dynamics without compromising people's privacy, mobility data reidentification opportunities and risks, and the MobiDataLab project.

Figure 5. The MobiDataLab Project at the 4th SoBigData++ Awareness Panel

Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

4.4. Collaboration with the MASTER Project

The overarching objective of **MASTER** (master-project-h2020.eu) is to form an international and inter-sectoral network of organisations working on a joint research programme to define new methods to build, manage and analyse multiple aspects of semantic trajectories. The RISE schema is based on the research carried out during the secondments of staff from European academic institutions to non-academic or international academic institutions.

Chiara Renso of CNR is the Project Coordinator, hence establishing cooperation between the two projects was immediate, especially taking into account that MASTER and MobiDataLab share many objectives.

First of all, the focus is on semantic enrichment. In MASTER it is intended as a very general link of raw trajectory data with different forms of contextual information. In MobiDataLab, this concept is instantiated into the Linked Open Data/RDF data representation settings, therefore the methods developed in MASTER can be tailored to fit the MobiDataLab Linked Open Data use case.

Secondly, both MASTER and MobiDataLab have a specific focus on the privacy aspect of mobility data and a general awareness that the more data is enriched with additional sources, the more the privacy of tracked individuals is at risk. A collaboration between MASTER and MobiDataLab was also planned in this respect. From privacy to ethics is a further step that was done in MASTER, since the project has appointed an Independent Ethical Advisor, Prof. Bettina Berendt, who is assisting the consortium in reflecting on the ethical issues of analysis in semantically enriched mobility data.

With the leadership of Prof. Berendt, MASTER partners Chiara Renso (CNR) and Prof. Stan Matwin (Dalhousie University) co-organised a Dagstuhl seminar Mobility Data Analysis: from Technical to Ethical, held January 8 to 12, 2022. The MobiDataLab coordinator Thierry Chevallier (AKKA) kindly accepted to participate in the seminar to give the MobiDataLab contribution to the seminar and therefore strengthen the link between the two projects also in this aspect.

MASTER organised a workshop on May 13, 2022, in Venice where Thierry Chevallier (AKKA) participated as a representative of MobiDataLab and exchanged results and open problems that can foster new future collaborations.

Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully, e.g., MobiDataLab has included a special article about the MASTER Project on its website, and the same article was furthermore disseminated within the second project newsletter.

4.5. Collaboration with the SYN+AIR Project

For **SYN+AIR** (syn-air.eu), collaboration among modes of transport relates to data sharing among Transport Service Providers (TSPs) enabling passengers to enjoy a seamless door-to-door travel experience. The main objective of SYN+AIR is to develop a Smart Contracts Framework, to tackle the aforementioned challenge.

AETHON is a SYN+AIR consortium member, hence establishing cooperation between the two projects was immediate, especially taking into account that SYN+AIR and MobiDataLab share several objectives.

A meeting between the two projects was organised on January 19, 2022, and SYN+AIR and MobiDataLab came up with potential fields of collaboration:

- Share documentation that might interest MobiDataLab and get feedback, and also consider integrating MobiDataLab findings into SYN+AIR work;
- Present a scientific paper together;

- Work together to add data transformation endpoints to the architecture of the Smart Contracts Framework solution presented;
- Co-organise a workshop on the topic of data sharing among TSPs.

Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

4.6. Collaboration with the REACH Incubator

REACH, the “EuRopEAn incubator for trusted and secure data value Chains”, (reach-incubator.eu) is an Innovation Action project funded by the European Commission and launched in September 2020. REACH is a second-generation Big Data incubator, building on the successful efforts of EDI – European Data Incubator to accelerate data-driven innovation in Europe, towards the vision of the Common European Data Space and developing the European Data Market.

REACH aims to be the main innovation mechanism that supports experimentations on secure and trusted data value chains across several sectors and the launching of new data-fuelled products and services to the market, leveraging the capacities of the best data-driven DIHs in Europe. Over its lifetime, REACH will support +100 business ideas from SMEs and select among them 30 solid business cases through a total of three open calls in the coming three years, distributing a total amount of €3.5M. Ultimately, REACH aims to demonstrate that Data Silos can be broken by enabling a multi-stakeholder cross-sectorial incubator to boost data-fuelled sustainable solutions. with the

Cooperation with the REACH Incubator is interesting for MobiDataLab since REACH has access to a pool of data-driven start-ups and SMEs to engage within the scope of the Living Labs (LL) and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs. This asset is valuable for MobiDataLab, especially taking into account the future organisation of hackathons, datathons, and codagons, which all require the presence of innovative data-driven individuals and third parties.

F6S is a REACH Incubator consortium member, hence establishing cooperation between the two projects was immediate, especially taking into account that REACH and MobiDataLab could both benefit from such cooperation.

Members of the MobiDataLab project have participated in REACH’s survey about data-driven industry insights and provided input on signals of disruptions and opportunities for growth within the industry, as well as first insight into current activities and challenges revolving around data and data value chains.

Moreover, both projects have agreed on mutual communication and dissemination support, which is being carried out successfully.

Future Collaboration Perspectives

This section refers to projects and initiatives to be considered for synergies and coordination (see Table 2), some even outside the spectrum of the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes.

5. This includes research projects and efforts that provide the space for joining scientific forces to promote science and/or broadening outreach to promote inclusiveness and stakeholder participation, whether MobiDataLab consortium members participate in these efforts or not.

Table 2. Tentative (not exhaustive) list of projects to be considered for synergies

Initiative Name	Project/Initiative Description	Potential Interest for MobiDataLab
Fenix Network	Fenix will develop the European federated architecture for data sharing serving the European logistics community to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms.	Learn from the experience of Fenix in terms of the business stakeholders' collaborative framework created and in terms of system architecture.
UNALAB - Urban Nature Labs	Foster urban innovation ecosystems, wherein stakeholders co-create and optimise nature-based solutions for improved climate and water resilience. Develop and demonstrate the capability of city-level open data platforms to accelerate NBS co-creation and implementation.	Key components and associated methodology for their definition in D2.1 'Legal and regulatory data sharing gap analysis' will be exploited along with a collection of the various definitions for Living Labs. Specifically, use the methodology for component definition and capitalise on the definition of roles from UNALAB. In addition, use UNALAB's "Tools for Co-creation" during the execution of its Living Labs. Possible liaison via the City of Genova, the Front-runner city in UNALAB.
DMS Accelerator	Supporting the European data market by providing free support services to data-centric SMEs and start-ups.	Have access to a pool of data-driven start-ups and SMEs to engage within the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs.
Y4PT - Youth for Public Transport	Y4PT's aim is to promote the active participation of young people on transport and mobility issues at all levels, and settings, since young people are one of the most significant groups of public transport users and will inherit the outcomes of all key decisions taken today.	Have access to a pool of relevant transport end-users to engage within the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs.

Inspire Knowledge Base	The INSPIRE Directive establishes an infrastructure for spatial information in Europe to support Community environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment. It entered into force in May 2007.	This pioneering EU-scale initiative in the field of environmental data has a lot to teach in terms of standardization, metadata management, cross-border data exchange, Linked Open Data, cloud solutions and Technical Guidelines.
Navitia.io - The open API for building cool stuff with transport data	Navitia.io provides an easy-to-use and standardized open API for accessing passenger information systems based on public transport open data. Navitia has already integrated over 1,500+ networks in 30+ countries globally. Navitia portal is used by start-ups, technology companies, academia and researchers: 11,000 users performing 6.8 Billion API requests per year.	HOVE is a member of Navitia.io that brings its expertise in open data and passenger information system for public transport.
Open Street Map	OpenStreetMap (OSM) is a mapping project that aims to build an open-source geographic database of the world, using GPS and other open-source data in a crowdsourcing data governance model (it is often referred as the 'Wikipedia of maps'). The OSM project is a great success, with more than 6 million registered users and contributors.	The OSM community develops a lot of excellent tools for searching, adding and improving transport data (bus stops, train stations, roads, lines, etc) and any other related geodata (infrastructure, building, etc). The MobiDataLab approach is to rely as much as possible on these open-source tools and to contribute to their improvement (e.g., providing feedback, adding resources) and to contribute, as an OSM user, to the OSM database when missing information is found (missing tags, missing poi, invalid polygon, etc.)
GeoNetwork	The GeoNetwork open-source project is a free and open source (FOSS) cataloguing application for spatially referenced resources. It is a catalogue of location-oriented information. GeoNetwork aims at providing an easy-to-use web interface to search geospatial data across multiple catalogues.	AKKA has adapted and deployed GeoNetwork for customers in various domains (Geology, Weather, Cultural Heritage, etc.) and will use its experience to reuse and adapt interoperability components for the MobiDataLab Reference Data Catalogue.
Open Geospatial Consortium	OGC API standards define modular API building blocks to spatially enable Web APIs in a consistent way. OGC API Features specifies the fundamental API building blocks for interacting with features (the term 'feature' is used by the spatial data community for anything of interest in the real world). OpenAPI is used to define the reusable API building	MobiDataLab will follow the innovative process the OGC has chosen for defining this new standard, including the animation of a developer's community, the establishment of in-person hackathons and remote validations via GitHub. To define this new "Features API" (aka WFS3.0) standard, the OGC relied heavily on

	blocks with responses in JSON and HTML.	the W3C best practices. These will also drive core integration guidelines and solutions in the Transport Cloud. Impact on the activities and standardization committees for spatial and mobility data.
IDSA - International Data Spaces Association	IDSA is a coalition of more than 130 member companies that share a vision of a world where all companies self-determine usage rules and realize the full value of their data in secure, trusted, equal partnerships; and we are making that vision a reality.	Impact on the activities of the three working groups: Architecture, Certification, Use cases & Requirements. This association will be approached via the T6.5 'Cooperation with other projects and initiatives' activities.
AIOTI - Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation	To drive on behalf of its members business, policy, research and innovation development in the IoT & Edge Computing and other converging technologies across the Digital Value Chain to support digitization in Europe, and competitiveness of Europe.	Impact on the activities of the Working Group 9 "Smart Mobility". This association will be approached via the T6.5 'Cooperation with other projects and initiatives' activities.
ITF – International Transport Forum	The International Transport Forum at the OECD is an intergovernmental organisation with 63 member countries. It acts as a think tank for transport policy and organises the Annual Summit of transport ministers. ITF is the only global body that covers all transport modes. The ITF is administratively integrated with the OECD, yet politically autonomous.	Impact on research activities addressing Big Data, Open Data and Transport Models. This association will be approached via the T6.5 'Cooperation with other projects and initiatives' activities.
UNIFE - Association of the European Rail Industry	The association advocates on behalf of more than 100 of Europe's leading rail supply companies – from SMEs to major industrial champions – active in the design, manufacture, maintenance and refurbishment of rail transport systems, subsystems and related equipment. UNIFE also brings together national rail industry associations from 11 European countries.	Impact on the "Digitalisation" and "Technical" working bodies.
UITP - International Association of Public Transport	As a passionate champion of sustainable urban mobility, UITP is internationally recognised for its work to advance the development of this critical policy agenda. UITP has a long history to its name and is the only worldwide network to bring together all public transport stakeholders and all sustainable transport modes.	Impact on the "IT & Innovation" and "Transport & Urban Life" working bodies.

5.1. Possible Barriers to Project Collaboration

It is important for partners to be aware of **potential barriers** to inter-project collaboration, such as:

- Individual personalities and competition between partners from the related EU projects. Naturally, this could be a barrier as some of the identified EU projects which will be involved in the collaboration efforts will have similar goals and objectives similar to those pursued by MobiDataLab, and might also have to compete with geographical, financial and stakeholder interests which must be considered by the MobiDataLab consortium.
- Lack of information and experience can be a potential barrier as sometimes other projects may be working to a different scope or mandate.
- As inter-project collaboration is a joint venture aimed at exploring how to refine or develop project outcomes, there should be expected that there can also be resistance to change.

As a result, there are various **risks** associated with inter-project collaboration including i) lack of consistency and clarity on roles and responsibilities; ii) outcomes do not justify the time and resources invested; iii) loss of flexibility in working practices, and complexity in decision-making; iv) energy and resources away from core aims, i.e., mission drift; and v) damage to organisation and waste of resources if collaboration is unsuccessful.

The possible barriers and risks identified above which can potentially limit the effectiveness of inter-project collaboration can be **mitigated** by developing the following: i) good personal relationships; ii) written agreements (e.g., Memorandum of Understanding); iii) clear and agreed mutual benefits and collaborative advantage; iv) focus on the big picture, and v) careful planning.

6. Monitoring and Lessons Learned

The monitoring of this activity is done by F6S, and partners are asked to inform F6S, as task leader, and POLIS, as WP leader, of any potential collaboration, and provide the necessary content for scheduling an initial meeting and further developing the collaboration.

In addition, the **Collaboration Log** (Figure 6) has been created, for regular monitoring and reporting on the progress of cooperation initiatives. All intended collaboration meetings should be reported to F6S so that they can be well documented.

Any collaborative publication or outcomes resulting from such collaboration approaches should also be saved accordingly in the file management system in the folder "T6.5 - Cooperation with other projects and initiatives" within the main folder Work Package 6.

Other discussion points or concept contributions which can potentially contribute to the MobiDataLab outputs should also be documented in a word document report and saved in the file management system. Where collaboration with other projects has informed or contributed to the successful execution of a task this should be documented in the associated deliverable under a section entitled 'Summary of Synergies and Collaborations'.

Drawing from the contents of the task folder within the project repository, the outcomes of the collaboration approaches will be outlined in a section in the MobiDataLab mid-term and final reports.

Project/Initiative	Funding body	End Date	Project/Initiative description	Potential interest for MobiDataLab	Activity status (select from options)	Lead partner	Status
Fenix Network	Connecting Europe Facility		Fenix will develop the European federated architecture for data sharing serving the European logistics community in order to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms	Learn from the experience of Fenix in terms of the business stakeholders' collaborative framework created and in terms of system architecture	Identified (tbc)	ICOOR (through 3rd party UNIMORE)	
Master - Multiple Aspect Trajectory Management and Analysis	H2020	déc-23	The research objective of MASTER is to investigate methods for building and analysing semantically rich mobility data	Build on the research results regarding the semantic enrichment activities. Specifically, on the new concept of multiple aspects trajectories methods, methods to manage these kinds of mobility data and	Completed	CNR is one of the consortium partners	https://www.dagstuhl.de/en/program/calendar/semhp/?semnr=2022 - Article on MobiDataLab and cooperation with MASTER in the 6th MASTER newsletter March-April 2022 (author, Thierry Chevallier)
SoBigData++ - European Integrated Infrastructure for Social Mining and Big Data Analytics	H2020	December 2024	Deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data to understand the complexity of our society. SoBigData++ will produce tools and services to Foster urban innovation ecosystems, wherein stakeholders co-create and optimise nature-based solutions for improved climate and water resilience. Develop and demonstrate the	Exploit the results in terms of: know how on a platform for sharing datasets and analysis methods. This can be exploited in the Transport Cloud and Use Cases	Completed	CNR is one of the consortium partners	Meeting on 9 November, between 3pm and 4pm CET/Brussels Time. These are the contacts for H2020 SoBigData++: josep.domingo@urv.cat (myself, Josep Domingo-Ferrer, URV), chiara.renso@isti.cnr.it (Chiara Renso, CNR), valerio.grossi@isti.cnr.it (Valerio Grossi, CNR), for
UNALAB - Urban Nature Labs	H2020	November 2022	The EU-funded REACH project will launch a sustainable European second-generation incubator for data-fuelled start-ups and SMEs with the aim of developing innovative experiments within data value	Have access to a pool of data-driven startups and SMEs to engage with in the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs	Identified (tbc)		
REACH - EuRopEAn incubator for trusted and secure data value CHains	H2020	February 2024	Supporting the European data market providing free support services to data-centric SMEs and start-ups	Have access to a pool of data-driven startups and SMEs to engage with in the scope of the Living Labs and other activities of the project that involve close contact with innovators and entrepreneurs	Completed	F6S is one of the consortium partners	
DMS Accelerator	H2020	December 2022	The EU-funded PolicyCLOUD project will deliver an integrated cloud-based environment for data-driven policy management. The environment will provide decision support to public authorities for policy	In recent years, the data market has been flourishing. A sharp downfall in trust towards platforms considered secure and privacy-aware, however, has hampered the market. This lack of trust has hit the SYN+AIR aims to develop common sets for data sharing between transport service providers (TSPs), enabling passengers to enjoy a seamless door-to-door	Identified (tbc)	F6S knows one of the consortium partners, Bright Pixel	
Policy Cloud - Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management	H2020	December 2022	TRUSTS - Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space		Identified (tbc)	F6S knows one of the partners, ICCS	
TRUSTS - Trusted Secure Data Sharing Space	H2020	December 2022	SYN+AIR - Synergies between transport modes and Air transportation		Completed	F6S knows one of the partners, Leibniz University	
SYN+AIR - Synergies between transport modes and Air transportation	H2020	December 2022			Completed	AETHON is one of the consortium partners	

Figure 6. MobiDataLab Cooperation Log

The following are the **lessons learned** in terms of how to identify synergies and create collaborations, and how to get maximum outcomes from the collaborations.

How to **identify synergies** and create collaborations:

- Early identification of relevant initiatives that could potentially have synergies with the project.
- Identify areas or objectives of collaboration (i.e., similar scope and activities, similar research objectives, similar target audiences, similar communication channels used, etc.).
- Early engagement with potential initiatives/stakeholders (i.e., sending a brief presentation email introducing the project, organising an awareness event early in the project).
- Take advantage of the activities conducted in the project for networking and relationship building (i.e., if the project foresees interviews for research purposes use that opportunity to negotiate mutual communication support; in events carefully track the contacts made and potential areas of future collaboration).

How to get **maximum outcome** from the collaborations:

- Organise joint events (both online and offline), collaborating in the identification and invitation of relevant speakers and panellists and getting maximum visibility through joint dissemination.
- Write joint conclusions and articles and support the dissemination to reach a wider audience.
- The collaboration online through social networks can exponentially contribute to increase the visibility and outreach of research results. Find and follow other projects and initiatives collaborating with the project, share their information, and send direct messages when you want to announce specific information.

Conclusion

The objectives of Task 6.5 'Cooperation with other projects and initiatives are being carried out according to the project's needs, and **continuous synergies** with other projects, initiatives and networks were implemented.

Creating synergies is an important task that is in continuous implementation throughout the duration of the project, and it is mostly sustained by the key involvement of project partners in other relevant initiatives and projects. Being transparent about the activities of the project opened several collaboration opportunities with other projects and increased the quality of the processes and results of MobiDataLab.

As part of MobiDataLab project activities, project partners have undertaken several actions to further develop the project, create synergies, disseminate the results achieved and find a link with other initiatives funded by the European Commission. As presented in the previous chapters, all project partners have used their contacts and links to other projects and further deepened their knowledge in terms of future Mobility Data sharing cloud solutions.

Considering that the mean of milestone verification is that "cooperation is established by tangible actions such as exchange of data or joint workshops to share practice around transport data", it can also be concluded that **Milestone 16** (MS16) 'Cooperation with other projects is also achieved successfully.

MobiDataLab Consortium

The consortium of MobiDataLab consists of 10 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks and industry sector specialists.

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